

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAFINA ANAS bearing USN 6SU20CC001 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAKHITHA A B bearing USN 6SU20CC002has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsALBIN TOM ANI bearing USN 6SU20CC003has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMITHA RAJ bearing USN 6SU20CC004 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsANUSHA S bearing USN 6SU20CC005 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVIKA K P bearing USN 6SU20CC006 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDHANYA DEVASSY bearing USN 6SU20CC007 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LAKSHMI PRASAD bearing USN 6SU20CC008 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMADHURA bearing USN 6SU20CC009 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMALHARUDHEEN K P bearing USN 6SU20CC010has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED AFLAH K bearing USN 6SU20CC011 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVANI E S bearing USN 6SU20CC012 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsPRAJEESHA BINO bearing USN 6SU20CC013has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsR PALLAVI bearing USN 6SU20CC014 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsRAZI RAZAK P C bearing USN 6SU20CC015 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA S bearing USN 6SU20CC016 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMMA MOHAMED bearing USN 6SU20CC017 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMMA O S bearing USN 6SU20CC018 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHANAMOL bearing USN 6SU20CC019 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHELHA V bearing USN 6SU20CC020 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSHOBLE K MATHEW bearing USN 6SU20CC021 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSTHUTI DINESH bearing USN 6SU20CC022has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SYED ABDUL KHALIQ bearing USN 6SU20CC023 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VEENA VIJAYANATHAN bearing USN 6SU20CC024 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNUPRIYA BIJUMON bearing USN 6SU20CC025 has completed his/her internship at Sortis Hospital Bangalore in the first Semester of the Cardiac Care technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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